

Defining spatiotemporal structure of vegetation anomaly in Cameroon in relationship with rainfall between 2000 and 2013 using remote sensing data

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Abstract

Remote sensing images play an essential role in the understanding of surface conditions, particularly in regions where in situ data are lacking. For example, high temporal resolution images allow to monitor vegetation activity and to specify evolution trends. The main objective of this study was to analyze the recent spatio-temporal evolution of vegetation activity measured in each of the 360 subdivisions of Cameroon in relation to the rainfall from 2000 to 2013. The data used are NDVI (Normalized Difference Vegetation Index) satellite images from the SPOT-VEGETATION (SPOT-VGT) sensor and rainfall product TAMSAT (Tropical Applications of Meteorology using SATellite) Rainfall Estimate (RFE) version 2.0. We used Moran I index and Anselin's local Moran I index to evaluate the spatial autocorrelation at the Global and Local scales.

The analysis of the relationship between NDVI and Rainfall was performed using Geographically weighted regression (GWR). The results obtained confirm the hypothesis of the existence of a spatial dependence between the different subdivisions of Cameroon on the spatial variability of vegetation activity. Moreover, this variability can be explained both spatially and temporally by the influence of rainfall. This influence is particularly strong in the Sudanese and Sahelian zones of the country where an increase in vegetation activity is observed between 2008 and 2013 following an increase in rainfall. Therefore, although human activity plays an important role in the spatio-temporal evolution of vegetation activity at the local level, i.e. within the different subdivisions of Cameroon, its influence is limited at finer scale compared to that of rainfall during this period.

Keywords : Remote sensing, NDVI, Rainfall, SPOT-VGT, TAMSAT RFE, Cameroon

Résumé

Les images de télédétection jouent un rôle primordial dans la connaissance des états de surface notamment dans les régions où les données in situ sont manquantes. Les images à grande résolution temporelle permettent par exemple de réaliser un suivi de l'activité végétale et de préciser des tendances d'évolution. Cette étude avait pour objectif principal d'analyser l'évolution spatio-temporelle récente de l'activité végétale mesurée au sein de chacun des 360 arrondissements du Cameroun en lien avec celle de la pluviométrie de 2000 à 2013. Les données utilisées sont les images satellites du NDVI (Normalized Difference Vegetation Index) issues du capteur SPOT-VEGETATION (SPOT-VGT) et de la pluviométrie (TAMSAT - Tropical Applications of Meteorology using SATellite version 2.0). Nous avons utilisé l'indice de Moran (I de Moran) et Anselin's local Moran I index pour évaluer l'autocorrélation spatiale au niveau Global et Local. L'analyse de la relation entre le NDVI et

la Pluviométrie a été réalisée en utilisant le Geographically weighted regression (GWR). Les résultats obtenus confirment l'hypothèse de l'existence d'une dépendance spatiale entre les différents arrondissements du Cameroun concernant la variabilité spatiale de l'activité végétale. De plus, cette variabilité s'explique tant sur les plans spatial que temporel par l'influence de la pluviométrie. Cette influence est particulièrement forte dans les zones soudanienne et sahéenne du pays où s'observe un renforcement de l'activité végétale entre 2008 et 2013 suite à une hausse de la pluviométrie. Dès lors, bien que l'activité humaine joue un rôle important dans l'évolution spatio-temporelle de l'activité végétale au niveau local, i.e. au sein des différents arrondissements du Cameroun, son influence semble se limiter à une échelle plus fine face à celle des précipitations entre 2000 et 2013. Ce résultat est conforme avec les observations faites précédemment par d'autres auteurs.

Mots clés : Télédétection, NDVI, Précipitations, SPOT-VGT, TAMSAT RFE, Cameroun

1. Introduction

In developing countries, such as those in Central Africa, poverty, population growth and concerns related to the economic development of states or communities have an immediate impact on ecosystem dynamics and environmental conservation policies (Bremner J. et al., 2010; Mosnier A. et al., 2014). In the case of forest ecosystems, the transformations, whether positive (regeneration) or negative (degradation), observed at local level are very often the result of human activities (Mayaux P. et al., 2003; de Wasseige C. et al., 2014; Hirschmugl M. et al., 2014; Tyukavina A. et al., 2018; Kleinschroth F. et al., 2019). They thus appear to be the main drivers of transformation of these ecosystems at this scale (Megevand C., 2013; Gillet P. et al., 2016; MINEPDED, 2016), which tends to minimize, if not evade, the direct influence of other drivers such as rainfall with which they are closely linked (de Wasseige C. et al., 2015), even though they are at the origin of changes observable over the long term (Zhou L. et al., 2014).

Thus, various studies have focused on the question of the role of rainfall in enhancing the vegetation activity observed in Africa since the early 2000s. Overall, they show that this increase in activity is due to an increase in rainfall observed at both local and sub-regional levels (Dardel C. et al., 2013; Gond, V. et al., 2013). This increase follows the long period of drought from the early 1970s to the 2000s (Ozer P. et al., 2003; Nicholson S.E., 2013; Evan A.T. et al., 2015; Maidment R.I. et al., 2015), which affected the region and increased anthropogenic pressure on plant resources, particularly in the Sahelian zone (Ariori S.L. et al., 2005). This positive regional dynamics of vegetation was also observed in different regions of the world for the period 1980-2013 more or less in connection with an increase in rainfall (de Jong R. et al., 2011; Liu Y. et al., 2015; Zhang Y. et al., 2017; Zhao L. et al., 2018). It therefore seems interesting to question the role of rainfall in vegetation dynamics observed at local and regional scales.

In this study, we are specifically interested in the recent spatio-temporal evolution of vegetation activity in Cameroon in relation to that of rainfall. Indeed, previous studies have highlighted an increase in vegetation activity observed within most sub-divisions in Cameroon since 2000 (Matsaguim

N.C.A. et al., 2020), particularly those located above 6°N (Djoufack-Manetsa V., 2011). We analyze its evolution at the local level (sub-division) in order to look for a spatial organization scheme likely to highlight clustering phenomena, or local specificities. Our analysis considers on the one hand the spatial dimension and on the other hand the temporal dimension of the evolution of the vegetation activity by formulating the hypothesis that there is a spatial configuration of the vegetation activity measured at the local level which accounts for a dynamics on a larger scale. Through an analysis of the global and local spatial autocorrelation, we identify the geographical areas where the dynamics are globally positive and those for which there are negative dynamics. In addition, we try to explain this dynamic with that observed at the level of precipitation.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Material

2.1.1. Study Area

The chosen study area is Cameroon, one of the six countries of the Congo Basin (Figure 1). It is located between 02-13°N and 09-16°E. It has a surface area of about 475,000 km². Its population was estimated in 2010 at 19,406,100 inhabitants unevenly distributed within 360 sub-divisions (BUCREP, 2010). Sub-divisions correspond to the basic administrative units. In biogeographical terms, Cameroon comprises six main ecosystems, the most widespread of which are the tropical savannah wooded ecosystem (166,000 km², or 34.87% of the territory) and that of dense tropical rainforest (226,000 km², or 47.48% of the territory) (Onana J.M., 2018). Figure 1 shows the different types of vegetation cover encountered in Cameroon between 2000 and 2007. They come from the results of the classification of NDVI images from the SPOT-VEGETATION sensor with a resolution of 1,000 m carried out by Verhegghen A. et al. (2012) for the entire Congo Basin. The results from Cameroon are shown in Figure 1 which shows 17 land cover classes.

2.1.2. Data description

2.1.2.1. Vegetation activity data

The vegetation activity observed in each sub-division of Cameroon was measured using a biophysical index; Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI). The NDVI is positively or negatively correlated to climatic parameters such as rainfall, evapotranspiration or temperature (Ji L. and Peters

Figure 1 : Study area and vegetation cover types in Cameroon (source : Verhegghen A. et al., 2012)

A.J., 2004; Li H. et al., 2016). It therefore allows the capture of the response of vegetation to climatic variations at different spatial scales (Kogan F. et al., 2003; Jiang N. et al., 2013). Thus, a database of satellite images composed of NDVI synthesis products from the SPOTVEGETATION (SPOT-VGT) sensor onboard the SPOT 4 and SPOT 5 satellites with a pixel resolution of 1 km² has been compiled. These images are freely available on the Flemish Institute for Technological Research (VITO) website at <http://free.vgt.vito.be>. The procedures for pre-processing and acquisition of these data are described by Deronde B. et al (2014). The time window covered by the database used for this study represents 14 years (01/01/2000 - 12/12/2013). The NDVI SPOT-VGT data have been widely used to characterize the baseline phenology of the vegetation at the different scale (Lasaponara R., 2006; Verger A. et al., 2016).

2.1.2.2. Rainfall data

In the context of studies on the spatial variability of climate parameters such as precipitation, the

use of satellite precipitation estimation products or "Rainfall Estimate" (RFE) has become an alternative when the network of rainfall stations is weak and the meteorological data discontinuous in time. To this end, a number of products are now available at the African scale. Among the most widely used are the TAMSAT (Tropical Applications of Meteorology using SATellite) synthesis products with a spatial resolution of 0.0375° x 0.0375°, or about 4km x 4km. For our study, we have chosen to use these data. They are TAMSAT RFE synthesis products. These data are based on thermal infrared images from the METEOSAT meteorological satellite provided by the European Organisation for the Exploitation of Meteorological Satellites (EUMETSAT). The infrared images are calibrated using in-situ data from a network of weather stations across the continent. The distribution of the weather stations used and the procedure for calibrating TAMSAT data are described by Tarnavsky et al (2014). The TAMSAT RFE data are listed in a database: TAMSAT African Rainfall Climatology And Timeseries (TARCAT)

whose development is described by Maidment R.I. et al. (2014). We have used version 2.0 of this TARCAT database, which can be downloaded at <http://www.tamsat.org.uk/cgi-bin/data/index.cgi>. The data used cover the same period as that covered by the NDVI data.

2.2. Methods

2.2.1. Data aggregation

NDVI and precipitation data have different spatial resolutions. We first resampled the NDVI data to bring them to the same spatial resolution as the rainfall data. Subsequently these two datasets were reprojected in the same geographic coordinate system as the data representing the boundaries of the different sub-divisions of Cameroon. Using Zonal statistical tool, mean value of NDVI and sum of rainfall were calculated for each sub-division of the country by year. At the end of the data aggregation process, each sub-division had 14 NDVI and 14 rainfall values for the period 2000 - 2013.

2.2.2. Spatial Statistics: Detecting Spatial Autocorrelation

To measure spatial dependence of vegetation anomaly at the global scale, we used methods derived from spatial statistics. These methods allow us to calculate indices that measure spatial autocorrelation within geographic data. Spatial autocorrelation is the correlation, positive or negative, of a variable with itself due to the spatial location of the observations (Feuillet T. et al., 2018). Spatial autocorrelation indices measure the spatial dependence between values of the same variable at different locations in space. The more the values of observations are influenced by the values of observations that are geographically close to them, the higher the spatial autocorrelation (Feuillet T. et al., 2018). Among these indices, we can distinguish those that measure dependence at the global scale: Moran's I index; and those that measure it at the local scale: Anselin's local Moran I index.

To be able to find hot spot or Cluster and outlier in our data, we used one spatial statistical tools: hot spot analysis and cluster and outlier analysis (Anselin's local Moran's I). Hot spot analysis tool was used to identify statistically significant spatial clusters of high values (hot spots) and low values (cold spots). The cluster and outlier analysis was used to identify clusters of heterogeneous values where sub-divisions

with high values of NDVI statistics are surrounded by sub-divisions with low values, or inversely.

However, the results of these different tools for measuring spatial autocorrelation depend closely on the conceptualization of spatial relationship that has been used (Feuillet T. et al., 2018). It is therefore very important to correctly choose the right conceptualization of the spatial relationship approach. This choice depends on the phenomenon being studied and the type of geographic data used (point, line or polygon) (ESRI, 2020). We have retained as a criterion of neighbourliness Queen contiguity of order 1 based on our data type.

2.2.3. Geographically Weighted Regression: Spatial Lag and Spatial Error Models

Geographically weighted regression (GWR) can be performed in the presence of spatial autocorrelation. GWR accounts for distinctions between spatial similarity between the dependent and independent variables. Ordinary least squares (OLS) and other simple statistics do not do this. Spatial lag models (SLM) and spatial error models (SEM) are two types of GWR. Spatial lag models produce a spatially lagged variable on the right hand side of a regression equation. A spatial error model (SEM) considers the estimation of maximum likelihood of a spatial regression model that includes a spatial autoregressive error term on the right hand side of the regression equation.

Moran's I was calculated to determine if spatial dependence was an issue. If the data was determined to be spatially autocorrelated, then a series of LaGrange multiplier (LM) test statistics were computed. The results of the LM would then indicate which GWR model, spatial lag model or spatial error model would be used in the final analysis.

3. Results

3.1. Measurement of the global spatial structure of vegetation activity from 2000 to 2013 in Cameroon

To evaluate the spatial heterogeneity of the NDVI anomaly over the whole of Cameroon, we used Moran's I index. It varies between -1 (negative spatial autocorrelation: neighbors have opposite values) and +1 (positive spatial autocorrelation: neighbors have similar values, existence of a cluster structure of spatial units). The spatial autocorrelation is null when the index is close to 0 (Feuille T. et al.,

Figure 2: Evolution of Moran's I statistic applied to NDVI anomaly data for the period 2000-2013. The global spatial autocorrelation test was performed with 999 permutations (p -value=0.0010).

2018). This index therefore measures the degree of similarity of values (hereafter, NDVI anomaly) between neighbouring spatial units (hereafter, subdivisions) at the scale of the entire study area.

In this study, all Moran's Index I values calculated for the period 2000-2013 are significantly positive with a critical value of $p=0.0010$ (figure 2). It indicates that these values are geographically concentrated. Data on NDVI anomalies measured at the scale of each subdivision in Cameroon show spatial similarity with Moran's Index I values that range from 0.70 in 2000 to 0.68 in 2013. However, its values vary annually with a minimum of 0.56 in 2003 and a maximum of 0.80 in 2002 (figure 2). With respect to rainfall anomalies also measured at the subdivision level for the same period, the higher Moran I Index values indicate a greater geographical concentration at the global level (figure 2). They range from a low of 0.76 in 2010 to a high of 0.96 in 2001. This seems normal given the type of data used (Rainfall Estimates).

3.2. Analysis of the local spatial autocorrelation of vegetation activity from 2000 to 2013

However, Moran's statistic is a global statistic that does not allow us to evaluate the local structure of spatial autocorrelation. To do this, the Local Indicator of Spatial Association (LISA) was used (Feuille T. et al., 2018). These local cluster detection methods was usefull to determine whether, for each spatial unit, similar NDVI anomaly values are observed in neighbouring units. They have thus permit to reveal regional trends.

The spatial variability of NDVI anomalies measured at the scale of the different sub-divisions of

Figure 3: Evolution of the local spatial structure of the NDVI anomaly for the period 2000-2013 in Cameroon. The global spatial autocorrelation test was performed with 9999 permutations (p -value=0.0010).

Cameroon between 2000 and 2013 shows a regional trend. Figure 3 highlights the existence of regional clusters according to whether the vegetation activity observed at the local scale (hereafter, a subdivision) presents a positive (High-High) or negative (Low-Low) spatial dynamic. The measurement of local spatial autocorrelation allows to underline statistically significant spatial discontinuities at the threshold p -value=0.0010 (Figure 3). Thus, in 2000 and 2001, negative regional dynamics of vegetation activity were observed mainly in the southern part of the country where forest ecosystems dominate. On the other hand, positive regional dynamics are observed mainly in the Sahelian zone. This apparent latitudinal discontinuity is more apparent in 2001, in contrast to 2000 (figure 3). Between 2002 and

Table 1: Results of Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) analysis and Regression diagnostics on NDVI anomaly

Years	2000	2001	2002	2003	2004	2005	2006	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013
OLS ESTIMATORS														
R-squared:	0.03 1154	0.12 2644	0.10 1335	0.00 3333	0.02 4858	0.11 8542	0.23 8009	0.003 219	0.235 901	0.000 088	0.003 742	0.04 0941	0.38 1027	0.10 4770
Adjusted R-squared:	0.02 8448	0.12 0193	0.09 8824	0.00 0549	0.02 2134	0.11 6079	0.23 5880	0.000 434	0.233 766	- 0.002 706	0.000 959	0.03 8262	0.37 9298	0.10 2269
F-statistic:	11.5 119	50.0 442	40.3 685	1.19 715	9.12 609	48.1 451	111. 822	1.156 01	110.5 25	0.031 3362	1.344 6	15.2 824	220. 378	41.8 972
Prob (F-statistic):	0.00 0768 873	7.95 431e -012	6.39 364e -010	0.27 4627	0.00 2701 05	1.86 354e -011	6.33 383e -023	0.283 021	1.043 1e- 022	0.859 612	0.246 998	0.00 0110 728	3.47 927e -039	3.17 047e -010
REGRESSION DIAGNOSTICS														
TEST ON NORMALITY OF ERRORS														
TEST	PROBABILITY													
Jarque-Bera	0.00 010	0.00 000	0.00 002	0.00 075	0.00 227	0.41 051	0.48 257	0.331 97	0.059 88	0.000 01	0.000 73	0.00 056	0.00 722	0.00 007
DIAGNOSTICS FOR HETEROSKEDASTICITY														
RANDOM COEFFICIENTS														
TEST	PROBABILITY													
Breusch-Pagan test	0.18 733	0.00 088	0.01 327	0.61 794	0.07 288	0.51 561	0.57 616	0.331 97	0.256 40	0.248 27	0.099 82	0.15 388	0.56 314	0.71 471
Koenker-Bassett test	0.18 943	0.00 130	0.01 388	0.56 622	0.08 057	0.51 417	0.54 308	0.555 42	0.206 19	0.291 05	0.062 52	0.11 949	0.50 838	0.67 766
DIAGNOSTICS FOR SPATIAL DEPENDENCE														
FOR WEIGHT MATRIX : Queen (row-standardized weights)														
TEST	PROBABILITY													
Moran's I (error)	0.00 000	0.00 000	0.00 000	0.00 000	0.00 000	0.00 000	0.00 000	0.00 000	0.000 00	0.00 000	0.00 000	0.00 000	0.00 000	0.00 000
Lagrange Multiplier (lag)	0.00 000	0.00 000	0.00 000	0.00 000	0.00 000	0.00 000	0.00 000	0.00 000	0.000 00	0.00 000	0.00 000	0.00 000	0.00 000	0.00 000
Robust LM (lag)	0.09 340	0.11 849	0.00 007	0.08 472	0.00 060	0.06 889	0.00 009	0.25 969	0.005 91	0.14 407	0.00 735	0.00 002	0.00 115	0.00 951
Lagrange Multiplier (error)	0.00 000	0.00 000	0.00 000	0.00 000	0.00 000	0.00 000	0.00 000	0.00 000	0.000 00	0.00 000	0.00 000	0.00 000	0.00 001	0.00 001
Robust LM (error)	0.99 362	0.67 017	0.31 439	0.18 126	0.14 487	0.33 494	0.88 406	0.43 538	0.582 44	0.16 566	0.05 849	0.03 556	0.20 347	0.60 468
Lagrange Multiplier (SARMA)	0.00 000	0.00 000	0.00 000	0.00 000	0.00 000	0.00 000	0.00 000	0.00 000	0.000 00	0.00 000	0.00 000	0.00 000	0.00 001	0.00 001

2008, this latitudinal discontinuity seems to have reversed, as can be observed in 2002, 2006, 2007 and 2008 (figure 3). During these years, clusters of

negative NDVI anomalies are observed mainly in the northern part of the country dominated by savannah ecosystems; while positive ones are mainly observed

Table 2: Spatial lag regression model and Regression diagnostics on NDVI anomaly

Years	2000	2001	2002	2003	2004	2005	2006	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013
SPATIAL LAG MODEL - MAXIMUM LIKELIHOOD ESTIMATION														
R-squared:	0.705 470	0.726 631	0.811 248	0.573 892	0.792 682	0.677 498	0.772 193	0.575 185	0.757 584	0.649 079	0.796 658	0.768 388	0.766 747	0.691 917
REGRESSION DIAGNOSTICS														
DIAGNOSTICS FOR HETEROSKEDASTICITY														
RANDOM COEFFICIENTS														
TEST	PROBABILITY													
Breusch-Pagan test	0.007 72	0.574 07	0.041 88	0.415 60	0.626 10	0.720 71	0.931 76	0.386 33	0.813 02	0.543 76	0.205 26	0.936 38	0.673 43	0.039 11
DIAGNOSTICS FOR SPATIAL DEPENDENCE														
SPATIAL LAG DEPENDENCE FOR WEIGHT MATRIX : Queen (row-standardized weights)														
TEST	PROBABILITY													
Likelihood Ratio Test	0.00 000													

in the south of the country. From 2009 to 2013, the latitudinal discontinuity seems to have reversed again (figure 3). However, there is a regional trend of positive NDVI anomalies that is more widespread and is observed over a very large part of the country. Clusters of sub-divisions with negative NDVI values appear mainly in the south-western part of the country near the coastal zone (figure 3).

In view of the results from the measurement of the local spatial autocorrelation of NDVI anomalies presented in figure 3, it seems obvious that the mechanism behind it must have spatial dynamics on a larger scale. In other words, the spatial structuring of the NDVI anomalies observed between 2000 and 2013 shows the influence of factors that operate at spatial scales larger than the sub-division scale.

3.3. Analysis of the influence of rainfall on the spatial dynamics of vegetation activity from 2000 to 2013

In order to highlight the influence of rainfall on the spatial structuring of NDVI anomalies, we used Geographically Weighted Regression (GWR) which takes into account the existence of spatial autocorrelation at the NDVI data level. Indeed, the analysis of the influence of rainfall on the spatial structuring of the NDVI anomalies without taking

into account the spatial dependence from the Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) Regression shows that rainfall explains at best only 38% (R-squared and Adjusted R-squared - 2012) of the observed spatial variability of NDVI at the local scale (table 1). In most years, its influence remains quite small, sometimes less than 10% as in 2000, 2004 and 2011 for significant results (Prob (F-statistic) ≤ 0.05) (table 1). However, the results from the OLS are influenced by the presence of autocorrelation in the NDVI data. This is shown by the diagnosis of the influence of spatial dependence (Table 1). Moran's I (error) proved to be highly significant (p value = 0.000000) all years indicating that spatial autocorrelation was an issue with the data. The first two tests (LM-error and LM-lag) were both significant, indicating that the robust models are more appropriate. The robust versions were to be considered only if the standard versions were significant. In this instance, both LM-lag and LM-error were significant, so the robust versions were then used. The Robust LM-error statistic was not significant (p value ≤ 0.05) all the years, but the Robust LM-lag statistic was (p value ≤ 0.05) most of the years. Therefore, a spatial lag model is used to remove any spatial autocorrelation.

Table 2 shows the results of the spatial lag regression model on NDVI anomalies. It can be seen that by

Figure 4a: Typology of Cameroonian sub-divisions according to their temporal profile of NDVI (left) and rainfall (right) anomalies from 2000 to 2013. The classification method used is the K-means method without spatial constraint (top) and with spatial constraint (bottom)

eliminating the influence of spatial autocorrelation in the NDVI data, the influence of rainfall on the spatial structuring of locally observed NDVI anomalies is reinforced. Indeed, apart from some years (2003, 2005, 2007 and 2009) where its influence is less than 70% (table 2), all other years, rainfall explains between 70 and 81% of the observed spatial variability. Moreover, the results are all positive, reflecting a linear and positive relationship. Therefore, the low plant activity (negative NDVI anomaly) recorded within a sub-division between 2000-2013 was mainly explained by low precipitation (negative rainfall anomaly) that was also low there; and vice versa.

3.4. Analysis of the influence of rainfall on the temporal evolution of vegetation activity from 2000 to 2013

By evaluating the role of rainfall on the temporal dynamics of vegetation activity between 2000 and 2013 compared to the average condition, it appears that it is positively related to rainfall. This is shown in figures 4a and b.

Figure 4a shows the results of the classification of Cameroonian sub-divisions according to their NDVI

temporal profiles using a variant of the approach used by Matsaguim N.C.A. et al., (2020). Indeed, given the presence of spatial dependence between the sub-divisions (figure 3), the K-means partitioning algorithm including a spatial constraint was used. Taking into account the spatial relationship between the sub-divisions allowed to obtain an identical classification of the latter, whether it is about NDVI anomalies or rainfall. The figure 4a, show the results of the classification operation to be compared by not taking into account the spatial relationship between the different sub-divisions (figure 4a - top) on the one hand, and by taking it into account on the other hand (figure 4a - bottom). 05 clusters were retained. The inclusion of the spatial constraint forces the classification algorithm to create spatially contiguous clusters with relatively similar temporal profiles.

Figure 4b shows the average phenological and rainfall profiles for the different clusters obtained by including the spatial constraint and presented in figure 4a. The two temporal profiles are superimposed one on top of the other to facilitate the comparison between each one. Concerning the temporal dynamics of vegetation activity within the different sub-divisions, it shows a positive trend in four (04) clusters. These are clusters 1, 3, 4 and 5 (figure 4b). The fundamental difference between them is mainly based on the year in which this positive trend appears. Contrary to the sub-divisions belonging to Clusters 1 and 4 where the vegetation activity is experiencing a positive phase since the years 2003-2004, those belonging to Clusters 3 and 5 are experiencing a much more recent resurgence of vegetation activity which seems to be directly related to an increase in rainfall given the pattern of rainfall anomalies. These results confirm the trends shown in figure 3.

Indeed, an analysis of the correlation between the average temporal profiles of NDVI and rainfall for each of the clusters presented in Figure 4b shows a direct link of rainfall on the phenological trajectories at the level of Cameroon's sub-divisions (table 3). Table 3 shows the results of the Pearson correlation test (p -value = 95%). There is a strong and positive influence of rainfall on the evolution of vegetation activity within the sub-divisions belonging to clusters 2, 3, 4 and 5. This influence is very strong at the level of the sub-divisions belonging to clusters 3, 4 and 5 which are located in the northern and eastern part of the country. Matsaguim N.C.A. et al. (2020)

Figure 4b: Characterization of the average temporal profiles of NDVI (Histograms) and rainfall (black curve) between 2000 and 2013. Red indicates negative NDVI anomalies, while blue indicates positive anomalies

Table 3: Relationship between the average temporal profiles of NDVI and rainfall between 2000 and 2013

	Cluster 1	Cluster 2	Cluster 3	Cluster 4	Cluster 5
Pearson Coefficient (<i>r</i>)	0.5168683	0.7039976	0.8281229	0.8450599	0.8989408
Pearson R-Squared (<i>R</i> ²)	0.2671528	0.4956126	0.6857875	0.7141262	0.8080945

have shown that it is in these parts of the country, i.e. particularly in the Far North, the North and the Adamawa regions, where vegetation activity shows some revival. It therefore appears that this is due to a probable increase in rainfall that would have been recorded from 2006 or 2008, especially in the northern part of the country (clusters 3 and 5) which has a Sudano-Sahelian climates.

4. Discussion

Spatial interactions between spatial units can be assessed using methods derived from spatial statistics. This is a set of methods that allow describing and visualizing spatial distributions, identifying atypical locations and end points, detecting spatial association patterns, and finally suggesting spatial patterns or other forms of spatial heterogeneity. In the framework of this study, we were able to demonstrate the existence of spatial dependence between the vegetation activity observed within a sub-division and that observed in its neighbors over the course of a year. With the help of NDVI, it was thus highlighted

the existence of a spatial pattern scheme of the vegetation activity observed at the local scale (figure 3). Similarly, it was shown that this pattern is very strongly positively related to rainfall (table 2). This is also true at the temporal scale (table 3).

These results complement those previously obtained by Matsaguim N.C.A. et al. (2020) who analyzed the temporal dynamics of vegetation activity from 2000 to 2013 within the various sub-divisions of Cameroon compared to the situation observed in 1999. They thus highlighted a positive dynamic of vegetation activity observed in nearly 50% of the country's sub-divisions. It was observed mainly in the regions located in the northern and eastern parts of the country. It would seem that the main factor at the origin of this enhancement of the vegetation activity is rainfall. However, it is important to note that these results are partly related to the data we used, especially with regard to rainfall data which certainly contain estimation errors (Balas N. et al., 2007; Agha Kouchak A. et al., 2012; Toté C. et al., 2015), and to the scale of the data analysis.

Indeed, the NDVI and rainfall data were aggregated at the sub-division level, which had the effect of eliminating the localized variations present within them. It seems obvious that this has influenced our results. However, regarding the dominant role of rainfall on vegetation activity in Cameroon, Djoufack-Manetsa V. (2011) already demonstrated that rainfall was the main determinant of vegetation cover evolution north of the 1000 mm/year isohyet between 1999 and 2008 on a larger scale. This is also what our results show (Table 3) despite the difference in scales and rainfall data used.

Nevertheless, the weaker correlation between NDVI and rainfall in the south-western part of Cameroon (clusters 1 and 2) indicates that rainfall is not the only factor explaining the dynamics observed there during this period (Table 3). Other factors certainly play a predominant role with the pressure of human activities on vegetation cover due to population growth and urban expansion in the foreground (Djoufack-Manetsa V., 2011). For example, this is shown by the work of Liu Y. et al. (2015), Zewdie W. et al. (2017) and Matsaguim N.C.A. et al. (2020). It is also likely that other climatic factors also play a more determining role than rainfall on the vegetation activity in those zones (clusters 1 and 2), as indicated by Zhao L. et al. (2018), NDVI is temperature-limited at northern high-latitudes, but water-limited in arid and semi-arid regions, and radiation-limited in the tropical rainforests. Furthermore, the nature and intensity of the relationship between NDVI and different climatic parameters varies according to the type of vegetation cover, regions of the world and the main climatic limiting factor for vegetation growth (Kogan F. et al., 2003; Zhao L. et al., 2018).

5. Conclusion

At the end of this study whose objective was to analyze the recent spatio-temporal evolution of vegetation activity in Cameroon in relation to that of rainfall thanks to NDVI, we can retain that at the spatial level, the vegetation activity observed at the level of the various sub-divisions of Cameroon is not totally independent of that recorded within its immediate neighbors. Taking into account this spatial dependence thus makes it possible to bring out patterns of spatial association which have enabled us to bring out a form of spatial heterogeneity between on the one hand the regions of the country where positive vegetation activity is observed, and on the

other hand those where it is negative. However, this spatial heterogeneity is not stationary but varies from one year to another, giving rise to different spatial patterns. The existence of this local spatial autocorrelation therefore takes into account the fact that the main factor at the origin of the variability of vegetation activity observed within the sub-divisions of Cameroon between 2000 and 2013 acts on a larger spatial scale. This is particularly the case with rainfall whose probable increase observed between 2006 and 2013 is at the origin of the increase in vegetation activity observed mainly in the sub-divisions located in the Sudanese and Sahelian zones of the country. However, these results are partly related to the data sets used, whether it is NDVI or rainfall. Therefore, it would be very interesting as a follow-up to this work to use other datasets to compare and validate the results. Similarly, it would also be interesting to question whether or not the renewed vegetation activity observed both at the national level and at the level of the entire Congo Basin will be maintained.

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